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METROSEXUALITY AS A MODE OF ENGAGING WITH REALITY IN “THE PSYCHIC CHALLENGE” (FROM PICKUP ARTISTS TO INFORMATION COACHES AND PSYCHICS)

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Gender and Cultural Contradictions in Television

Modern television, especially in its entertainment domain, continues to serve as a space where gender stereotypes, narcissism, and social role-playing intersect. A prime example is the show “The Psychic Challenge” — a project that appears to be mystical but, in reality, illustrates profound contradictions regarding masculinity, femininity, and power.

The portrayal of “intelligent,” “polite,” or “reserved” men often reveals that their silence stems from an awareness that their spoken words would likely be inappropriate, vulgar, or crude, eliciting negative reactions in any self-respecting cultural environment. This silence becomes a defense mechanism, a strategy to maintain their image as “well-behaved boys.” As the saying goes: “Silence is golden.” Yet, when such individuals speak, they often expose their superficial thinking, narcissism, and lack of depth, previously masked by their silence.

Television characters frequently embody exaggerated personas designed to evoke strong emotional responses from viewers. For instance, Namtar Enziga, a caricatured pickup artist from the 2000s, exemplifies hyperbolic narcissism. He assumes roles such as a “demonologist,” “necromancer,” and “gloomy sorcerer” while remaining an ordinary, insecure man whose image relies heavily on visual attributes such as eyeliner and a slicked-back hairstyle [7]. His character becomes a metaphor for compensating inner emptiness with external appearances.

Transformations and Drug-induced Escapism as a Means of Coping with Reality

Dmitry Matveev, the winner of the twentieth season of “The Psychic Challenge,” represents another example. Initially an insecure teenager, he transformed into a figure embodying a rock-and-roll lifestyle. After moving to China, he drastically altered his appearance through facial plastic surgery, cheekbone lifts, and numerous tattoos. He married a Chinese woman named Astrid, but their marriage soon dissolved, leading Matveev to relocate to Thailand, where he indulged in drug use and authored the book *“Devil-May-Care: The Paranormal Addict”* [6].

This book serves as a form of apology for his drug-fueled escapades, exposing the wounded and distorted soul of an individual attempting to hide behind an external façade. Matveev candidly shares his traumas, addictions, and internal void, emphasizing how “The Psychic Challenge” contributed to his self-destruction. This raises critical questions about how television

projects exploit participants without considering their psychological and emotional well-being.

Metrosexuality and Its Manifestations

Alex Sheps, the winner of Season 14, serves as an emblematic representation of metrosexuality within the framework of the television show. His meticulously curated appearance — comprising tailored suits, ornate rings, and skull-themed T-shirts — reflects an elaborate self-presentation strategy. Sheps enhances his image through dyed hair, colored contact lenses, and artificial fangs, constructing the persona of a “brooding vampire.” However, beneath this carefully crafted facade lie struggles with substance addiction, manipulative tendencies, and profound personal insecurities.

Sheps adeptly leveraged his interpersonal relationships with fellow contestants to consolidate his status on the show and cultivate an aura of enigmatic romanticism. His connection with transgender contestant Ilona Novoselova, alongside a prolonged romantic involvement with Marilyn Kerro, became central narrative arcs across multiple seasons. Ilona Novoselova, a former season 7 winner, openly expressed her support for Sheps despite acknowledging his narcissistic and manipulative behavior. Within their dynamic, Sheps frequently assumed a dominant role, exploiting Ilona’s emotional attachment for strategic advantage.

Marilyn Kerro, another significant figure in Sheps’ narrative, also experienced the detrimental consequences of his toxic influence. Despite her genuine affection and unwavering support, Sheps subjected her to repeated public humiliation, dismissing her as insufficiently powerful as a witch [3]. Their eventual separation was marred by public scandals, including allegations of intimate video blackmail. This controversy emerged as a pivotal moment in the show’s history, underscoring the extent to which personal relationships were instrumentalized to drive viewer engagement and boost ratings.

In Episode 13 of Season 2, Marilyn Kerro was placed in a challenging scenario when Alex Sheps was invited to assess her abilities [8]. The episode featured moments of theatricality, including Sheps' exposure of a tattoo on his younger brother Oleg's body, a revelation previously hinted at by contestant Angelina Izosimova [2]. The scene devolved into a spectacle, with elder Sheps and show host Basharov making macabre jokes about Marilyn Kerro, an incident she later publicly condemned on social media [3]. Another striking moment featured Alex Sheps engaging in an absurd phone conversation with his mother, in which he demanded to know whether she loved him more than his younger brother [1]. This episode symbolized the perpetual fraternal rivalry and their ongoing attempts to assert dominance over one another.

Speculation regarding Alex Sheps' personal life has remained a topic of public intrigue. Some fans and industry insiders have interpreted his refined fashion sense, mannerisms, and interactions with male contestants as indicative of a non-heteronormative sexual orientation. However, these assumptions remain speculative and largely rooted in public perception rather than substantiated evidence.

Gender Conflicts and Manipulation

The contentious relationship between Oleg Sheps and Angelina Izosimova constitutes another focal point of the show's interpersonal drama [4]. Oleg, the younger sibling of Alex, exhibits a pronounced inferiority complex, exacerbated by constant comparisons to his older brother. His frequent attempts to assert his value often culminate in public embarrassment. In confrontations with Angelina, Oleg resorts to threats and character defamation, tactics that ultimately highlight his vulnerability rather than his strength.

Oleg's behavior is profoundly shaped by unresolved maternal trauma, which manifests vividly in his emotional responses and interpersonal dynamics. A particularly poignant moment involved Oleg's candid confession about his childhood experiences of feeling neglected in favor of his elder brother.

Their mother, as Oleg recounted, appeared to offer more overt affection and validation to Alex, leaving Oleg with a persistent sense of inadequacy. This unresolved trauma fuels his relentless quest for validation, whether through confrontations with Angelina [2] or his performance in the show's challenges [4].

If Alex Sheps represents the archetype of a “dark, mysterious vampire,” Oleg embodies a contrasting persona — a romantic hero seemingly drawn from a Turkish melodrama. However, beneath his polished exterior lies a complex web of insecurities and learned behavioral patterns, shaped by years spent in the shadow of his older brother's fame and manipulative tendencies. Oleg's reliance on charm and his cultivated image of a “handsome hero” reflects both his coping mechanisms and the pressures of living up to public expectations.

Despite projecting the image of a Childe Harold-esque romantic figure or a “prince on a white horse,” Oleg's behavior frequently aligns with the patterns of an insecure pickup artist rather than a genuinely confident individual. His discomfort with romantic dynamics is palpable, and his insecurity often bleeds into his performative interactions. This insecurity is further highlighted by his foray into self-help coaching, culminating in the creation of a paid training program titled “*7 Steps to Love*” [5].

Ultimately, the Sheps brothers' contrasting personas — Alex's calculated darkness and Oleg's polished romanticism — serve as a microcosm of the broader themes of manipulation, insecurity, and the performative nature of reality television. Their interactions, shaped by familial trauma and personal ambition, offer viewers a dramatic lens through which to examine the human condition in highly mediated spaces.

Masculinity Through the Lens of the Show

Vlad Cherevaty presents a more traditional representation of masculinity. His character embodies the “everyman,” approachable and relatable. However, his personal traumas and quest for audience approval make him

dependent on external validation. Though he appears as a “village hero,” his simplicity conceals profound vulnerabilities and emotional struggles. His remark, “You should be giving birth,” directed at a female participant, encapsulates his stereotypical view of women’s roles.

Alexander Sakov, another character, offers a contrasting portrayal. Cast as a rural eccentric who works with raw meat, he embodies a grotesque aesthetic. Scenes of gore, darkness, and scattered entrails serve as an off-putting yet theatrical representation of his supposed communion with the dead. One viral moment features him holding animal entrails with the caption: “Get yourself together.” His exaggerated persona adds an element of trash entertainment to prime time, amplifying the show’s ratings while satirizing archetypal masculinity in an unsettling form.

Ethics and Public Perception

Despite its entertaining nature, “The Psychic Challenge” raises serious questions about how such projects influence perceptions of gender and social roles. A notable example involves Olga Yakubovich, who was subjected to aggressive remarks by Alexander Sheps, stated that he had “blinded her doll”, accusing her of being a “weak witch” [3; 8]. Her candid response exposed the narcissism and overt arrogance of her accuser. This incident exemplifies how the show manipulates conflicts to boost ratings while simultaneously prompting ethical debates about acceptable boundaries in media.

Viewers often adopt a “hate-watching” stance, condemning participants’ behavior while simultaneously being drawn to it. This ambivalence is a key factor in the show’s popularity. Scenes involving insults aimed at Nadezhda Shevchenko — such as Alex Sheps calling her an “old alcoholic” — or emotional provocations directed at Viktoria Raidos, become focal points for social media debates, shaping audiences’ contradictory perceptions.

The confrontation between Angelina and Oleg Sheps demonstrates Oleg’s deep traumas. His maternal trauma, combined with the constant shadow of

his older brother, creates in him an irresistible desire to prove his superiority. However, this superiority often manifests itself through destructive behavior and emotional instability. At the same time, the conflict with Angelina reflects her ability not only to cope with external challenges, but also to bring elements of intellectual debate to the show.

Notably, the show serves as a platform for addressing complex social issues. For example, the conflict between Oleg Sheps and Angelina Izosimova embodies a struggle for gender equality, highlighting the challenges women face in patriarchal media structures [2]. However, beyond the show's narrative, questions linger about the extent to which it manipulates these conflicts for ratings [4].

Conclusion

“The Psychic Challenge” represents a unique phenomenon in the media landscape, functioning simultaneously as an entertainment product and a platform for social experimentation. It demonstrates how archetypes of masculinity and femininity intersect with contemporary realities, exposing viewers to emotional and intellectual provocations.

Open questions surrounding participant exploitation, gender stereotypes, and inequality invite further discussion and analysis. The show acts as a mirror of society, reflecting its strengths and weaknesses. Through its characters, conflicts, and personal stories, viewers are not only entertained but also confronted with critical issues concerning human relationships, personal ambitions, and social recognition.

Ultimately, “The Psychic Challenge” transcends its mystical premise to become a reflection of societal dynamics, exploring the contradictions inherent in gender relations and power perceptions. From metrosexual narcissists to traditional “everymen,” from strong women to toxic patriarchal norms, the show encapsulates the complexity and multifaceted nature of modern television. It provokes reflections on power, identity, and social

justice, turning entertainment into a forum for addressing significant societal questions.

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